

Artificial Intelligence and the Erosion of Human Morality: A Buddhist Inquiry into Technological Ethics

Nilesh P. Megnani

Department of Philosophy, SIES College, Mumbai

Corresponding Author – Nilesh P. Megnani

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Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is often depicted as an agency that would substitute or distort human morality. However, from a Buddhist perspective, AI itself owns no inherent ethical responsibility; it is merely a multiplier of human intention. The moral erosion alleged on AI arises not from technology but from *trivisha*, (the three poisons) greed, hatred, and delusion causing human suffering. When these unwholesome afflictions impel the development and use of technology, AI becomes a mirror showing collective moral degeneration. Cognitive capitalism fuels *lobha* (greed) through compulsive digital engagement; algorithmic echo chambers increase *dvesha* (hatred) and extremism; and technological dependence intensifies *moha* (delusion) reducing mindfulness and self-reflection leading to moral erosion.

Through the lens of Buddhist principles such as *karma*, *pratityasamutpada* (interdependence), and *karuna* (compassion), this paper argues that AI should be dealt with as a dependent phenomenon that arises through causes and conditions. The ethical quality of the AI reflects the consciousness of its creators. The moral crisis, therefore, is a human one. The fundamental question is whether human is willing to give away autonomy of judgement and empathy regarding critical matters to algorithmic systems. The loss of autonomy certainly corrodes the inner fundamentals of human's ethical life.

To follow the 'middle way' is the Buddhist solution to this moral predicament. Human must engage with AI with mindfulness, compassion and accountability. The ultimate motive of AI developers, users, stakeholders and policy makers must be to diminish suffering and boost collective well-being. Ultimately, human consciousness is the cause and condition of the impending consequences of AI. Buddhist perspective recommends to avoid technological absolutism and rejection and rather endeavour to heighten humans' awareness and apply Right thought and Right action. Mindfully incorporated, AI can aid achieve the lofty moral goals of Buddhism viz. annihilation of suffering and attainment of liberation.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Moral Erosion, Buddhism, Three Poisons, Awareness, Compassion

Introduction:

The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has triggered a significant debate about its moral implications in various arenas in the contemporary world. It is often seen as a threat rather than an aid to human morality. AI is alleged to supersede and surpass human thought, decision-making power and could potentially harm society by magnifying prejudices and hostilities. However, this perspective overlooks the fact that ultimately it is human, their intentions and sanctions that form the basis of ethical impoverishment or enrichment. According to the Buddhist perspective, ethicality is not to be ascribed

to technology or AI but rather to the maker of it. Ethicality lies in the moral, mental and volitional agency in humans. Hence, AI is seen as an amplifier of the moral voice of human contributing to its conditions and sufferings. This paper emphasises that in fact *trivisha*, the three unwholesome afflictions of greed, hatred, and delusion shape human psychology and influence the socio-cultural and technological ethos of the world leading to moral erosion. AI is merely the outcome of the collective moral order that humans have generated by succumbing to the three afflictions. The paper attempts to enrich the understanding of AI ethics by

expounding the Buddhist doctrines of *karma*, *pratityasamutpada* (interdependence), and *karuna* (compassion). The paper questions the moral responsibility of AI developers, policy makers, stakeholders and users rather than the technology itself. Neither total rejection nor blind acceptance; the Buddhist perspective takes the middle path of conscious adoption of AI wherein humans' ethical responsibility is not shrugged off to technology. It prescribes that humans must be mindful, compassionate and responsible while developing and engaging with AI. The paper attempts to bring greater moral responsibility on humans in the debate of AI ethics by highlighting that AI like any other is a dependent phenomenon. Ultimately, human consciousness is the cause and condition of the impending consequences of AI and hence it must be the locus of ethical transformation.

Objectives:

1. To interpret AI ethics from the Buddhist point of view.
2. To showcase that discussion on AI ethics must be human-centric and not AI or technology-centric.
3. To propose ethical guidelines to governance, policy makers, industry and designers, and individuals.

Research Methodology:

The methodology of the research is reflective and logical, aiming to build theoretical coherence rather than empirical validation. The paper engages in a qualitative philosophical study based on interpretive and associative methods. It integrates primary ethical and philosophical concepts of Buddhism with secondary literature found on AI and AI ethics. Buddhist ethics and precepts are interpreted in an expository manner to obtain moral principles applicable to AI ethics.

Scope and Limitations:

The scope of this paper is philosophical and educational. It concentrates on ethical and

educational aspects rather than experimental or empirical case studies. The limitations of the study is that it adopts a non-quantitative approach and depends on explanatory analysis alone which is subjective. However, its merit lies in aligning ancient Indian knowledge with modern AI ethical frameworks for global interests.

AI Ethics and Buddhist Thought:

Overview of AI Ethics:

Deliberations on AI ethics have surged in various fields – philosophy, sociology, computer science, public policy, etc. Among the many issues that surround AI ethics are its bias in algorithm, black box system (opaque decision-making), creation of technology that is potentially capable of autonomous harm and life destruction, skewing judgements and behaviour through social media and breach of privacy. AI is also alleged to replace human resource and labour in near future which has created a panic in the society.

These discussions are essential but often circumvent human as the originator and director of AI. It presumes AI itself as the moral agent and projects human as a mere regulator of policies or at best a disaster manager. Rather, one must question and enquire into the moral responsibility of the designers, executors and the users of AI.

Buddhist Ethics and Technology:

Buddhist core philosophy that propagates non-violence, end of suffering and pursuit of enlightenment can contribute significantly to the deliberation of AI ethics. For example Buddhist's insistence on the need to alleviate the suffering of all through compassion or understanding the truth of conditioned existence of all phenomena may provide the normative fundamentals of AI ethics. Likewise, the Buddhist concept of dependent origination widens the horizon of discussion from individualistic to relational ethics of AI. Lin in his article, 'All about the human: A Buddhist take on AI ethics' suggests that AI ethics is not ethics of robots but ethics about robots. This is primarily because AI itself lacks consciousness and suffering unlike

humans. Hence, AI ethics must be a deliberation on humans' ethical responsibility towards the generation of AI and its prevailing and potential consequences. Ideally, human attributes like nurture, alertness and discernment cannot be transferred to technology or AI. The paper suggests that the ethical discussion must surround the human tendencies that ultimately play role in shaping AI technology and its usage viz. greed, hatred and delusion (Lin, 2023).

Three Poisons, Dependent Arising and Karma as Basis of AI Ethics:

The Buddhist precepts that are the basis of this discussion are: Three Poisons or three unwholesome roots called *trivisha*, Dependent arising i.e. *pratityasamutpada* (dependent arising) and Karma (action and consequence) concerning moral agency.

The Three Poisons:

According to Buddhism, the primary cause of unwholesome action are the three unwholesome states (*trivisha*) in human beings namely greed (*lobha*), hatred (*dvesha*) and delusion (*moha*). Greed implies craving, hoarding or over attachment to phenomena. Hatred could take the form of aversion, aggression and antagonism. Delusion is the misunderstanding of the true nature of things due to ignorance and unawareness. *Trivisha* perpetuates unwholesome actions, suffering and unending attachment to existence. A technological development rooted in such tendencies too perpetuates suffering. If the intentions of the stakeholders of AI technology are driven by the three poisons then its consequences too bear the unwholesome results. The seed invariably determine the fruit is the basic law of ethics in Buddhism.

Pratityasamutpada (Dependent Origination):

Buddhist precept of dependent origination (*pratityasamutpada*) holds that all phenomena are interconnected and a transient outcome of the chain of causes and conditions. AI too being one of the phenomena is an outcome of the cause and conditions created by humans. Hence, AI or AI systems are not independent moral agents but rather

conditioned by human intentions deeply imbedded in its design and deployment. AI is not an isolated phenomenon and its moral quality is a consequence of the moral character of the humans.

Karma (Action and Consequence):

In Buddhism the ethical value of an action lies in its intention. Compassion and wisdom lead to wholesome outcomes while malefic intentions rooted in greed, hatred, etc perpetuate negative consequences of suffering. AI itself does not have conscious intentions. The intentions of the developers, users, etc influence the consequences of the AI technology and hence, are the real moral agents responsible for their karmas and its consequences (Tharpa, 2018, p. 13-29).

The Three Poisons and Moral Erosion in AI systems:

Greed (*Lobha*) and Cognitive Capitalism:

In the modern digital age, greed is not only individual but also collectively institutionalised. Digital platforms are driven by greed and promote cognitive capitalism through the use of AI. Cognitive capitalism implies exploitation of information, knowledge and algorithmic data to seize attention and extort profit. Digital platforms – media and entertainment, service based, e-commerce or gaming, etc – monetise by designing strategies that constantly increase users' attention, clicks and engagement with the platform to generate revenue. These strategies are rooted in greed and unethical practices bombing the users with notifications, content, feedback/review loops and fake rewards. Human attention is seen as a source of money irrespective of its repercussions on their wellbeing.

Promoting and hankering for more likes, more shares, more attention and more on-screen entertainment are seen as greed from the Buddhist perspective. Such attributes intensify unwholesome states like passion and attachment obscuring the development of wholesome states like loving-kindness, mindfulness and wisdom. AI systems play a major role in breeding manipulative strategies and

providing crucial data to the developers and deployers.

According to Buddhist perspective, the principle of dependent arising gives the insight that greed-led designs are the outcome of addiction-generating algorithmic systems which are controlled and created after thorough human deliberation. These deliberations are rooted in greed and immoral intentions. The cause and conditions point out the moral erosion of the human and not AI inherently. As an antidote to this, the Buddhists suggest the practise of generosity, non-attachment and contentment. AI systems must be designed to encourage mindfulness in humans and discourage addictive behaviour. Profits can still be generated through value-based models that promote or do not hamper wellbeing. Development must be growth-centred and not profit-centred.

Hatred (*Dvesha*) and Algorithmic Echo-Chambers:

AI systems via algorithmic filtering are responsible for creating filter bubbles and encouraging echo chambers. Users' beliefs, prejudice and ideologies are reinforced through these to the extent that the users' world view becomes narrow and often radical. Extremism, polarisation, online antagonism and subsequent riots or violent outbursts can be ascribed to the reinforcement of stubborn viewpoints due to algorithmic filtering of content. According to Buddhism, mental states like these are denoted as *dvesha* i.e. hatred.

AI is intentionally designed to proliferate content that the user engages with even arbitrarily. In the bargain content triggering strong emotional reactions is flashed repeatedly to the users. Often, content sparking aggression, hate, aversion and disgust is presented to the user and they fall prey to a 'mental prison' that filter bubbles create on their slightest engagement.

Since, defending one's belief and ideology is ingrained in humans, the developers capitalise on their vulnerability and use AI systems to maximise engagement and monetise it for narrow selfish interest. Thus, various forms of hate - radicalisation,

ideological bias, cultural prejudice, tribalism, etc - are propagated in an unhinged way. The moral crises lies in the fact that humans intentionally create such systems and users volitionally succumb to the spell of the jinxed content.

According to Buddhist ethics, the remedy to hatred is loving-kindness (*metta*), compassion (*karuna*), and equanimity (*upekkha*). AI systems should be developed and consumed in ways that encourage understanding diverse viewpoints, respectful dialogue, and discourage extremism and hostility of any sort (Edmonds, 2024, p. 99-104).

Delusion (*Moha*) and Technological Enslavement:

Moha or delusion in Buddhism constitutes false views of self and reality, unawareness and ignorance. In the digital era this takes the form of (i) reduction in mindfulness on the part of the humans and delegating the crucial job of critical thinking and arriving at judgments (ex. in medical and judicial matters) to machines (ii) being delusional that AI is omniscient, autonomous, unbiased and objective and (iii) the belief that technology and AI is the panacea to all problems. These frames of mind are delusional and can damage the wellbeing of human race substantially.

AI apparent neutrality is delusional because in fact several biases and skewed values are imbedded in its responses by the power players for selfish interest. Buddhism believes that reality is impermanent, conditioned and lacks substantiality. As opposed to this there is an upsurge in the belief of general populace that technological outputs are unchanging truths. This can obscure their way to higher understanding of the nature of reality hampering humans' spiritual wellbeing. It could lead to the decline of mindfulness and self-responsibility and distort the path of moral development.

According to Buddhism, Right view, Right thought and the other limbs of the Eight-fold path must be developed and practiced consistently for moral development and spiritual growth. It implies the development of significant human traits like empathy, kindness and fairness in humans. If humans choose to delegate moral and other crucial

decisions to the algorithmic systems then not only the opportunity for moral development is missed, it also leads to the perpetuation of ignorance. Hence, Buddhists perspective would recommend to not surrender human autonomy and empathy to AI systems.

However, one must note that AI is simply creating a condition that encourages unawareness and moral deterioration. It is humans who are responsible and should ideally develop wisdom, and awareness of intention and action in developing AI systems and technology.

Viewing AI as Dependent Phenomenon:

The Buddhist principle of dependent origination implies that all phenomena are interconnected and conditioned. Everything including AI is a part and parcel of the dynamic interdependent flow of cause and condition; an unending series of unfolding of events in the repeated pattern of cause and consequence. In the context, AI is one of the event in the long chain of hardware development, software development, data, human design, social frameworks, regulatory outlines, economic agendas, etc. AI itself is not an independent phenomenon that can be ascribed with moral responsibility. Besides, it is unconscious. Thus, moral responsibility lies with each human involved as a designer, deployer, user, policy-maker or stake holder. Lin stresses that humans' moral responsibility continues because AI lacks conscious intention; nonetheless it remains a 'moral object' towards which humans have responsibilities. The erosion of human morality has taken place because human intentions are drenched in greed, hatred and delusion in creating, shaping and using AI. When massive destruction of life and property take place in wars with the use of nuclear weapons or automated weapons; the responsibility lies not with technology but with the builders of technology and decision makers of the war (Lin, 2023; Prado, 2016, p. 208).

Self-Determination, Empathy and the Deterioration of Ethical Life:

The foundation of morality is self-determination of judgement. It is the very basis of

the enduring human values of liberty, freedom and independence. To submit this foundation to AI systems is to reduce humanity to a weak vegetative entity devoid of critical thinking, empathy and moral deliberation. Such a world dominated by the judgements of AI systems would encourage reaction rather than reflection, imposition rather than moral deliberation and disintegration rather than wholeness. The real concern therefore is about human surrendering their moral responsibility and capacity to AI and not whether AI is morally responsible. The moral predicament lies in the erosion of human subjectivity itself.

If humans shrug off their moral responsibility to the algorithmic systems, they will weaken the basis of ethical life imperative for higher spiritual growth, according to Buddhism. Buddhism recommends practice of the Eight-fold path constituting right action, right speech, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness, etc to attain liberation. All this entails an active moral deliberation by a moral agency which is oneself. In the practice of the Eight-fold path lies the development of profound human attributes of empathy, loving-kindness and compassion. In this sense, submission of moral responsibility will imply also the submission of the possibility of liberation (Hongladarom, 2020).

Mindful Engagement with AI as the Middle Way:

Buddhism recommends the 'middle way' towards the acceptance of AI technology. AI technology cannot be completely rejected nor blindly accepted. It avoids the extremes of uncritical acceptance or technological absolutism. Over indulgence or attachment to it can lead to several psycho-physical hazards along with moral deterioration and dulling of awareness. Whereas, abstinence from or aversion towards it can hamper the potential growth of humans through its right management and usage. Buddhism advocates mindful engagement with AI technology right from its building to its end use such that it serves the purpose of alleviating suffering and propagating wellbeing and advancement of all sentient while being fully aware of its cons and fatal outcomes.

Developers, Users and Policy-Makers to Cultivate Mindfulness of Intention:

The aim for deploying AI systems must be alleviation of suffering and not amassing super-normal profits. Systems must be designed to exhibit compassion and empathy. It must attempt to alleviate prejudices, biases and harm of any sort.

Accountability and transparency must be raised. Humans must be aware of the data inputs as well as the results elicited by AI systems. If the process surpasses human deciphering as in advanced AI models then its results/judgements must be strictly scrutinised by human agency. Its moral and practical implications must be thoroughly weighed before implementation. The ultimate aim of AI technology should be to reduce suffering and encourage collective upliftment of human consciousness and joy.

In most fields like judiciary, medicine, education, etc, empathy, ethical deliberation and relational understanding is crucial and must not be blindly handed over to AI systems. AI systems should function as an aid to equip humans to take better and well-informed judgements. However, it should not replace human judgement or human agency altogether.

Thus, AI becomes an apparatus to help attain the Buddhist goals of the lessening of suffering, the fostering of insight, the recognition of interconnectedness of all, and eventually the attainment of liberation.

Recommendations:

Indicators for AI Governance and Practice:

From the preceding analysis following indicators may be drawn:

Policy and Governance:

The role of Government and policy makers can no more remain passive of passing safety regulations and fairness ordinances alone. It must build a human system that focuses, supervises and contributes to the incorporation of human intentions and values in the ecosystems that produce AI technology.

Government should encourage transparency, objectivity, answerability and human-centred AI designs inspired by Buddhist and yet universal moral insights. Principles of cause and condition, interdependence, alleviation of suffering and raising of mindfulness can serve as the universal pivot to frame policies or strategies concerning AI and allied technology.

Industry and Design:

Likewise, AI designers and engineers should also be nudged to incorporate the virtues of mindfulness, transparency and consideration for human wellbeing into system design. Awareness of one's own intentions, non-manipulative approach, empathy for users and communities, and responsibility for consequences must be evoked. The basic understanding of the Buddhist principle of the karma that intentional action creates consequences and one reaps only what one sows can be a guiding spirit for the AI design industry.

Individual Vigilance:

For the users, practices like meditation, mindfulness, self-reflection, awareness of habits pertaining technological usage, cultivation of empathy and kindness are utmost necessary in today's era. Moral development and vigilance has become imperative while engaging with any digital platform or any AI driven technology. If the users yield their attention and judgement submissively to algorithms then it only enfeebles their own moral capacities.

Limitations:

The paper obliquely assumes a general Buddhist ethic without distinguishing among the many Buddhist schools viz. Theravada, Mahayana and Vajrayana. More refined work could study how different traditions might perceive the role of the three-poisons pertaining AI development and engagement. Meticulous study and application of Buddhist moral principles to AI systems can be further explored.

The question of agency and moral status of AI itself, for instance - advanced AGI (Artificial

General Intelligence) a theoretical form of AI and robots with consciousness - stays philosophically open. Buddhist scholars too deliberate whether machines could ever be moral vehicles/agents. More philosophical and technical exploration will be needed (Edmonds, 2024, p. 204-208).

Conclusion:

The paper offer to express that the accusation of the erosion of morality on AI is false and that the moral responsibility lies with human intentions. The overindulgent and unethical environment pertaining digital world and the ethos that surrounds the creation and utilisation of AI is a consequence of the three poisons (*trivisha*) viz. greed, hatred and delusion entrenched in human behaviour due to lack of awareness and mindfulness.

The Buddhist way offers a middle path. It advocates neither denunciation of technology nor credulous acceptance of AI systems. AI creation, design and usage must be guided by mindfulness, empathy and responsible management. This is possible only when developers, users and communities uphold human autonomy of judgement and compassion. AI, if mindfully used, can aid alleviate suffering, cultivate wisdom and inculcate the understanding of interconnectedness.

Ultimately, AI may continue to influence and affect the world but the moral crises is for the humans to resolve. Human consciousness is both the cause and condition of the consequences of the various seeds it chooses to sow. In the hands of the sensitive, mindful, wise and compassionate human, AI can become instrumental in gaining material prosperity, attaining spiritual wellbeing and arriving at the highest goal of *nirvana* i.e. liberation.

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